

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL 2 (NEW RECORDS FOR THE RESEARCH AREA)

The results obtained from the study are as follows: In the present study, 80 species from eleven families are recognised, these families are Elmidae Curtis, 1830; Dryopidae Billberg, 1820; Gyrinidae Latreille, 1810; Halipidae Aubé, 1836; Helophoridae Leach, 1815; Heteroceridae Macleay, 1825; Hydrophilidae Latreille, 1802; Hydrochidae Thomson, 1859; Hydraenidae Mulsant, 1844; Noteridae Thomson, 1860 and Spercheidae Erichson, 1837. Individuals were collected and identified from the present study investigates the altitudes and coordinates of the following studying region (Figure 1), localities (SM-1) are to be noted for the material collected. With the exception of the first, second and third records, the following list details the new records for each province in the research area in Türkiye, along with their respective types and distributions [*ex.: number of samples collected; Lx: Location number (SM-1)]:

Family. Gyrinidae Latreille, 1810

***Gyrinus substriatus* Stephens, 1828**

Material examined. L₆₂, 23.06.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [4].

Distribution in the world. Spain, Portugal, Morocco and Turkey [10,11,63, 64].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

***Pelodytes caesus* (Duftschmid, 1805)**

Material examined. L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₅₇, 15.09.2020, 1 ex; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 2 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the research area [30].

Distribution in the world. Southern England, Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Finland, Germany, Poland, Czechia, Slovakia, Austria, Hungary, Ukraine, France, Spain, Portugal, Italy, Greece, Bulgaria, Romania, Turkey, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, and Iran [30, 65]

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

Family Halipidae Aubé, 1836

***Haliplus heydeni* Wehncke, 1875**

Material examined. L₃, 20.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 10 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 9 ex.; L₄₂, 26.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₉, 14.05.2021, 2 ex.; L₆₃, 26.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₅₅, 20.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₀, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the research area [30-32].

Distribution in the world. The United Kingdom, Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark, Germany, Poland, Czechia, Slovakia, Austria, Hungary, France, Belgium, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece, Bulgaria, Romania, Serbia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Slovenia, North Macedonia, and Albania, Turkey, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, western Siberia (Russia) and Turkestan [30-32, 62].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

Family Helophoridae Leach, 1815

***Helophorus (Helophorus) aquaticus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. L₂, 20.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₁₀, 20.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₁, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₈, 18.09.2020, 11 ex.; L₃₇, 21.08.2020, L₄₁, 23.07.2020, 1 ex.; 1 ex.; L₄₆, 22.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₄₉, 19.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₅₃, 22.07.2020, 3 ex.; L₇₀, 15.05.2021, 2 ex.; L₇₄, 15.09.2020, 8 ex.; L₇₇, 16.09.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [30-36].

Distribution in the world. Germany, Austria, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, the Netherlands, Iran, Spain, Israel, Sweden, Switzerland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Poland, Turkey and Russia (Western Siberia) [13, 34, 45].

Zoogeographical component. EUR [62].

Helophorus (Helophorus) syriacus (Kuwert, 1885)

Material examined. L₄, 30.08.2021, 1 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the research area [32,34,35].

Distribution in the world. Iran, Israel, Kazakhstan, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, Turkmenistan and Yemen [15,18,20,34]

Zoogeographical component. SWA [62].

Helophorus (Empleurus) nubilus (Fabricius, 1776)

Material examined. L₉, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₀, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.

Remark: This is the first registration for the research area [30-36].

Distribution in the world. Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Croatia, Switzerland, Czechia, Germany, Estonia, Finland, France, Great Britain, Georgia, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Monaco, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia [34,58].

Zoogeographical component. EUR [62].

Helophorus discrepans Rey, 1885

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₄, 30.08.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₉, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [36].

Distribution in the world. Austria, Belarus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Morocco, Finland, France, Croatia, Iran, Spain, Italy, Cyprus, Luxembourg, Hungary, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Turkey and Ukraine [34, 58].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

Helophorus (Atracthelophorus) daedalus (d'Orchymont, 1932)

Material examined. L₂₉, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₁, 20.07.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the research area [30-40].

Distribution in the world. Iran, Israel, Syria, Turkey and Jordan [34].

Zoogeographical component. SWA [62].

Helophorus (Eutrichelophorus) micans (Falderman, 1835)

Material examined. L₆, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₅₂, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 4 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [30-40].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Armenia, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Great Britain, Hungary, Slovakia, Russia: South European territory,

Ukraine, Afghanistan, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Pakistan, Tajikistan, Turkey, Uzbekistan [34,58]

Zoogeographical component. ASF [62].

Helophorus (Atracthelophorus) lewisi (Angus, 1985)

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 5 ex.; L₁, 18.06.2021, 5 ex.; L₃, 20.06.2020, 3 ex.; L₇, 18.09.2021, 12 ex.; L₈, 19.07.2021, 8 ex.; L₉, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₁, 21.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₁₉, 22.06.2021, 8 ex.; L₂₀, 22.06.2021, 3 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 10 ex.; L₂₂, 21.07.2020, 19 ex.; L₂₇, 20.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₃, 18.07.2021, 7 ex.; L₃₆, 20.08.2020, 10 ex.; L₃₆, 22.06.2021, 12 ex.; L₃₇, 21.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₄₃, 26.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₅, 19.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₄₇, 22.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₉, 19.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₅₁, 19.08.2020, 5 ex.; L₅₆, 18.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₄, 19.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₆₄, 26.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₆₈, 15.05.2021, 7 ex.; L₇₃, 14.05.2021, 6 ex.; L₇₇, 16.09.2020, 7 ex.; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 42 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the research area [30-40].

Distribution in the world: Georgia, Palestine, Israel, Russia, Syria, Turkey, and Jordan [34].

Zoogeographical component. SWA [62].

Helophorus oscillator Sharp, 1915

Material examined. L₆₂, 23.06.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the research area [32, 41].

Distribution in the world: Egypt (doubtful), Israel, Iraq, Syria, Turkey and Lebanon [66].

Zoogeographical component. MED [62, 66].

Helophorus (Rhopalhelophorus) obscurus Mulsant, 1844

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 4 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the studying region (Iğdır province) [32, 38, 41].

Distribution in the world. Germany, Austria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Morocco, Finland, France, Croatia, Netherlands, United Kingdom, Iran, Ireland, Spain, Sweden, Italy, Cyprus, Luxembourg, Hungary, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Turkey and Ukraine [24, 34].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

Helophorus arvernicus Mulsant, 1846

Material examined. L₆, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₉, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₃, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₂₉, 20.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₅₂, 24.06.2020, 5 ex.; L₅₃, 22.07.2020, 10 ex.; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 10 ex.; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₂, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₂, 23.06.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₃, 18.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₃, 26.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₆₈, 27.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₉, 14.05.2021, 1 ex.

Remark: This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [30-41].

Distribution in the world. Austria, Denmark, Finland, France, Italy, Norway, Russia, Spain, Scotland, Sweden and Turkey [34].

Zoogeographical component. EUR [62].

Helophorus griseus Herbst, 1793

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₂, 20.07.2021; 1 ex.; L₄, 30.08.2021, 1 ex.; L₁₂, 03.09.2021, 1 ex.; L₂₉, 18.09.2020, 2 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the research area [32,34,39].

Distribution in the world. Armenia, Azerbaijan, Europa and Turkey [58, 67].

Zoogeographical component. ASF [62].

***Helophorus brevivalpis brevivalpis* Bedel, 1881**

Material examined. L₉, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₄, 20.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₆₁, 19/08/2020, 64 ex.; L₂₅, 21.07.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₄, 14.08.2021, 2 ex.; L₄₂, 26.07.2020, 7 ex.; L₄₅, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₈, 26.06.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₅, 18.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₇₃, 14.05.2021, 2 ex.; L₇₄, 15.09.2020, 4 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [30-41,45].

Distribution in the world. Caucasus, Europa, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Lebanon, Syria and Turkey [58,67].

Zoogeographical component. TEM [62].

***Helophorus (Rhopalhelophorus) pallidipennis* (Mulsant and Wachanru, 1852)**

Material examined. L₅₃, 22.07.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [34,36,41,46].

Distribution in the world. Israel, Cyprus, Greece and Turkey [34]

Zoogeographical component. SWA [62].

***Helophorus (Rhopalhelophorus) hilaris* (Sharp, 1916)**

Material examined. L₂, 31.08.2021, 4 ex.; L₅, 21.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₅, 18.07.2021, 5 ex.; L₁₀, 20.08.2020, 15 ex.; L₁₃, 21.08.2020, 15 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 3 ex.; L₃₁, 19.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₃₆, 23.06.2021, 8 ex.; L₆₅, 25.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₅₅, 20.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₇₂, 15.05.2021, 9 ex.; L₇₆, 14.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₉, 20.08.2020, 6 ex.; L₄₂, 22.07.2020, 5 ex.; L₄₄, 25.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₄₉, 19.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₅₀, 18.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₅₀, 25.06.2021, 5 ex.; L₅₁, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₂, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₈, 18.08.2020, 3 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [30-41].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Caucasus, Iran, Lebanon and Turkey [58,67].

Zoogeographical component. SWA [62].

***Helophorus (Rhopalhelophorus) frater* (d'Orchymont, 1926)**

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 5 ex.; L₅₂, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [36,41].

Distribution in the world. China, India, Iran, Nepal, Russia and Turkey [34].

Zoogeographical component. TEM [62].

***Helophorus grandis* (Illiger, 1798)**

Material examined. L₂₉, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₄, 25.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₄₈, 26.06.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₄, 26.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₆₅, 18.08.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [41,43].

Distribution in the world. Albania, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Greece, Iran, Macedonia, Romania, Serbia and Turkey [34,58]

Zoogeographical component. EUR [62].

***Helophorus longitarsis* Wollaston, 1864**

Material examined. L₇, 18.09.2020, 2 ex.; L₉, 21.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₇, 22.07.2020, 1 ex; L₆₂, 23.06.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [32,34,41].

Distribution in the world. Austria, France, Great Britain, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Spain, Russia (South European Territory), Ukraine, Yugoslavia (Serbia, Montenegro), Canary Islands, Tunisia, Kazakhstan and Turkey [20].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

***Helophorus abeillei* Guillebeau, 1896**

Material examined. L₇₁, 15.05.2021, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the studying region (Iğdır province) [32,34,35,41,44].

Distribution in the world. Armenia, Iran, Israel, Lebanon, Syria and Turkey [34].

Zoogeographical component. MED [62].

***Helophorus nanus* Sturm, 1836**

Material examined. L₂₃, 21.07.2020, 4 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the studying region (Ardahan province) [32,41].

Distribution in the world. Germany, Austria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Holland, England, Ireland, Iran, Sweden, Switzerland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Nepal, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovenia, and Turkey [34].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

***Helophorus paraminutus* Angus, 1986**

Material examined. L₂₉, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₃, 26.07.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the studying region (Ardahan and Kars provinces) [32, 34, 35, 41, 44].

Distribution in the world. Germany, Austria, Hungary, Russia, Slovakia, Ukraine, Greece, and Türkiye [34].

Zoogeographical component. EUR [62].

***Helophorus dorsalis* Marsham, 1802**

Material examined: L₁, 20.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₁, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the studying region (Ardahan province) [33,41].

Distribution in the world. Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Britain, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Switzerland, Turkey and Ukraine [34].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

Family Hydrophilidae Latreille, 1802

***Hydrochara dichroma* (Fairmaire, 1982)**

Material examined. L₇, 28.08.2020, 9 ex.; L₃₁, 19.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₅, 14.08.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₅₉, 24.06.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₈, 27.08.2020, 2 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [34, 36, 41].

Distribution in the world. Bulgaria, China, Iran, Israel, Cyprus, Hungary, Uzbekistan, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Turkey, Ukraine, and Greece [34].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

***Hydrochara caraboides* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: L₂, 20.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₅, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₉, 19.08.2020, 2 ex. **Remark:** Recorded for the first time from the research area [34, 41, 44, 47].

Distribution in the world: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia, Croatia, Herzegovina, Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine, Yugoslavia, and Turkey [34].

Zoogeographical component: SIE [62].

***Hydrophilus piceus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [42].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Europa, Algeria, Egypt, Iran, Far East, Israel, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkey and West Siberia [58]

Zoogeographical component. ASF [62].

***Helochares obscurus* (O. F. Müller, 1776)**

Material examined: L₂, 20.05.2020, 2 ex.; L₂, 20.07.2021; 6 ex.; L₂, 31.08.2021, 3 ex. L₇, 28.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₇, 18.09.2021, 2 ex.; L₁₀, 20.08.2020, 21 ex.; L₂₄, 20.08.2020, 52 ex.; L₃₁, 19.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₂, 23.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₆, 23.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₂, 22.07.2020, 10 ex.; L₇₆, 14.05.2021, 2 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [48].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Europa, Iran, Israel, Kazakhstan, Turkey, West Siberia, China [58]

Zoogeographical component. ASF [62].

***Helochares lividoides* Hansen and Hebauer, 1988**

Material examined. L₅, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₅, 21.07.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₀, 18.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₃₃, 19.09.2020 2 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 4 ex.; L₅₇, 15.09.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [31, 41, 44].

Distribution in the world. Israel and Turkey [34].

Zoogeographical component. EEM [62].

***Helochares punctatus* Sharp, 1869**

Material examined. L₄₉, 19.08.2020, 2 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [48].

Distribution in the world. Israel, Turkey and Slovakia [5, 68]

Zoogeographical component. TUE [62].

***Helochares lividus* (Forster, 1771)**

Material examined. L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 8 ex.; L₅₈, 22.07.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [34,41,46,49].

Distribution in the world. Austria, Azerbaijan, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Greece Hungary, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, Poland, Russia, Turkey and United Kingdom [5, 34].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

***Anacaena limbata* (Fabricius, 1792)**

Material examined. L₃, 20. 06. 2020, 2 ex.; L₆, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₇, 18.09.2020, 10 ex.; L₇, 21.06.2020, 3 ex.; L₈, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₈, 19.07.2021, 4 ex.; L₁₀, 20.08.2020, 6 ex.; L₁₁, 21.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₁₃, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₅, 20.07.2020, 27 ex.; L₁₉, 22.06.2021, 3 ex.; L₂₂, 21.07.2020, 4 ex.; L₂₇, 20.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₁, 19.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₃₃, 19.09.2020, 2 ex.; L₃₃, 18.07.2021, 2 ex.; L₃₆, 22.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₅, 19.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₅₆, 18.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₂, 03.09.2021, 1 ex.; L₉, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₄, 20.08.2020, 22 ex.; L₆₁, 19/08/2020, 4 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 8 ex.; L₃₆, 23.06.2021, 3 ex.; L₃₄, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₄, 14.08.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₈, 26.06.2020, 3 ex.; L₆₄, 19.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₇₃, 14.05.2021, 2 ex.; L₇₆, 14.05.2021, 1 ex; L₇₈, 16.09.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [30-47,50].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Europa, Caucasus, Algeria, Far East, Iran, Israel, Kazakhstan, Syria, Turkey and West Siberia [58].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

***Anacaena lutescens* (Stephens, 1829)**

Material examined. L₅, 21.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₉, 21.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 5 ex.; L₄₅, 19.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₅₄, 26.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₄, 26.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₆₅, 25.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₆₈, 27.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₈, 15.05.2021, 5 ex.; L₇₁, 15.05.2021, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [34,41,50].

Distribution in the world. Austria, Belgium, Algeria, Canada, Czech Republic, Denmark, Egypt, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece Ireland, Netherlands, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Mexico, Norway, Portugal, Russia, Turkey and United Kingdom [34]

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

***Anacaena rufipes* (Guillebeau, 1896)**

Material examined. L₂, 20.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₆, 27.07.2020, 3 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 7 ex.; L₂₃, 21.07.2020, 10 ex.; L₂₃, 21.06.2021, 4 ex.; L₃₄, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₉, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₉, 14.08.2021, 3 ex.; L₄₉, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₀, 18.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₅₁, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₆, 18.08.2020, 1 ex; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₆₃, 18.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₃, 26.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₆₅, 25.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₇₀, 15.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₆₈, 15.05.2021, 4 ex.; L₇₅, 14.05.2021, 3 ex.; L₇₇, 15.05.2021, 4 ex.; L₈₀, 28.08.2020, 1 ex; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 2 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area. [30-47, 50].

Distribution in the world. Bosnia and Herzegovina, Greece, Israel, Italy, Lebanon and Turkey [34].

Zoogeographical component. TUE [62].

***Berosus guttalis* (Rey, 1883)**

Material examined. L₄₆, 22.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₈, 15.05.2021, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [41].

Distribution in the world. Algeria, France, Morocco, Spain, Tunisia and Turkey [15, 41].

Zoogeographical component. ASF [62].

***Berosus signaticollis* (Charpentier, 1825)**

Material examined. L₂₃, 21.07.2020; 1 ex.; L₃₅, 14.08.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₁, 23.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₄, 26.06.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₅, 25.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₆₆, 28.08.2020 1 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [41].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Europa, Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia, Afghanistan, Iran, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, West Siberia and Turkey [34, 58]

Zoogeographical component. ASF [62].

***Coelostoma orbiculare* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined. L₆, 27.07.2020, 6 ex.; L₁₈, 22.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 10 ex.; L₂₄, 20.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₅, 20.08.2020, 15 ex.; L₂₅, 21.07.2021, 5 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₅, 14.08.2021, 2 ex.; L₄₂, 26.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₄₉, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₄, 26.06.2020, 3 ex.; L₆₆, 28.08.2020 7 ex.; L₇₆, 14.05.2021, 2 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Iğdır provinces [30-47].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Armenia, Europa, East and West Siberia, China, Iran, Japan, Kazakhstan and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

***Paracymus aeneus* (Germar, 1824)**

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₉, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₃₃, 19.09.2020 2 ex.; L₆₄, 26.06.2021, 3 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [33, 41].

Distribution in the world. Albania, Algeria, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Cyprus, Denmark, Egypt, France, Croatia, Germany, Greece Ireland, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and United Kingdom [34].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

***Paracymus chalceolus* (Solsky, 1874)**

Material examined. L₃₆, 20.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₀, 18.08.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Iğdır provinces [41].

Distribution in the world. Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Uzbekistan and Turkey [15, 18, 34].

Zoogeographical component. TUE [62].

***Paracymus scutellaris* (Rosenhauer, 1856)**

Material examined. L₇, 28.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₈, 15.05.2021, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [36, 41].

Distribution in the world. Albania, Algeria, Belgium, Britain, Croatica, Cyprus, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Morocco, Netherlands, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Turkey [15, 18, 20, 32].

Zoogeographical component. MED [62].

Laccobius (Dimorpholaccobius) sipylus d'Orchymont, 1939

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₃, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₀, 18.08.2020, 10 ex.; L₆₈, 18.08.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [36, 41, 50].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Transcaucasia, Iran, Iraq, Lebanon and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. SWA [62].

Laccobius (Dimorpholaccobius) syriacus (Guillebeau, 1896)

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 3 ex.; L₂, 20.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₃, 20.06.2020, 6 ex.; L₄, 28.08.2020, 13 ex.; L₆, 27.07.2020, 62 ex.; L₇, 28.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₈, 21.07.2020, 12 ex.; L₈, 19.07.2021, 5 ex.; L₉, 21.08.2020, 10 ex.; L₁₁, 21.08.2020, 7 ex.; L₁₃, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₄, 22.07.2020, 13 ex.; L₁₅, 20.07.2020, 32 ex.; L₁₅, 17.07.2021, 15 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 4 ex.; L₁₇, 17.07.2021, 1 ex.; L₂₀, 22.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 20 ex.; L₂₅, 20.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₂₅, 21.07.2021, 8 ex.; L₂₇, 18.09.2020, 12 ex.; L₂₇, 20.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₃₀, 18.09.2020, 36 ex.; L₃₃, 19.09.2020, 4 ex.; L₃₅, 14.08.2021, 10 ex.; L₃₆, 20.08.2020, 13 ex.; L₃₆, 22.06.2021, 14 ex.; L₃₇, 21.08.2020 44 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 20 ex.; L₄₃, 26.07.2020, 5 ex.; L₄₄, 25.06.2021, 20 ex.; L₄₅, 19.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₃₇, 23.06.2021, 9 ex.; L₅₁, 19.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₅₂, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₄, 26.06.2020, 10 ex.; L₅₉, 24.06.2020, 3 ex.; L₆₄, 19.08.2020, 6 ex.; L₆₄, 26.06.2021, 10 ex.; L₆₉, 14.05.2021, 2 ex.; L₇₆, 14.05.2021, 3 ex.; L₇₇, 16.09.2020, 5 ex.; L₈₀, 28.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 3 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Iğdır provinces [30-50].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Transcaucasia, Europa, Algeria, Egypt, Afghanistan, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Lebanon, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. TEM [62].

Laccobius bipunctatus (Fabricius, 1775)

Material examined. L₉, 21.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₃₀, 18.09.2020, 4 ex.; L₃₁, 19.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₆, 23.06.2021, 2 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Iğdır provinces [34, 41, 50].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Georgia, Europa, Morocco, Tunisia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Turkey, West Siberia, China [58].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

Laccobius obscuratus aegaeus Gentili, 1974

Material examined. L₅, 21.08.2020, 7 ex.; L₇, 28.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₅₀, 18.08.2020, 10 ex.; L₁₄, 22.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₃, 18/08/2020, 1 ex.; L₃₄, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [16].

Distribution in the world. Greece and Turkey [34].

Zoogeographical component. MED [62].

Laccobius obscuratus obscuratus Rottenberg, 1874

Material examined. L₃₁, 19.09.2020, 20 ex.; L₂₄, 20.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₆₃, 18.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 4 ex.; L₂₉, 18.09.2020, 28 ex.; L₂₉, 20.06.2021, 32 ex.; L₄₉, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [16].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Transcaucasia, Europa, Cyprus, Iran, Lebanon, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Turkey [34 ,58].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

***Laccobius hindukuschi* Chiesa, 1966**

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₃, 19.09.2020 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [46, 50].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Transcaucasia, Russia, Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq, Kyrgyzstan, Pakistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Turkey and Uzbekistan [58].

Zoogeographical component. SWA [62].

***Laccobius sulcatulus* Reitter, 1909**

Material examined. L₇, 18.09.2021, 1 ex.; L₂₇, 20.06.2021 22 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Iğdır provinces [41 ,50].

Distribution in the world. Transcaucasia, Iran, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

***Laccobius (Dimorpholaccobius) simulatrix* Orchymont, 1932**

Material examined. L₈, 19.07.2021, 13 ex.; L₄, 28.08.2020, 13 ex.; L₆, 21.07.2020, 28 ex.; L₆, 23.06.2021, 17 ex.; L₇, 28.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₉, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₂, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₂, 03.09.2021, 1 ex.; L₁₃, 21.08.2020, 9 ex.; L₁₄, 22.07.2020, 3 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 11 ex.; L₁₈, 22.06.2021, 23 ex.; L₂₂, 21.07.2020, 6 ex.; L₂₄, 20.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₃, 18.07.2021, 5 ex.; L₃₃, 18.07.2021, 5 ex.; L₃₉, 20.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₁, 23.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₂, 22.07.2020, 13 ex.; L₄₆, 22.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₄₈, 26.06.2020, 2 ex.; L₅₂, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₅, 20.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 14 ex.; L₆₂, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₂, 23.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₃, 26.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₇₄, 15.09.2020, 4 ex.; L₆₆, 28.08.2020 6 ex.; L₆₇, 27.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₆₈, 18.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₈, 15.05.2021, 4 ex.; L₆₉, 14.05.2021, 27 ex.; L₇₁, 15.05.2021, 15 ex.; L₇₇, 15.05.2021, 10 ex.; L₇₅, 14.05.2021, 3 ex.; L₇₇, 16.09.2020, 15 ex.; L₇₈, 16.09.2020, 2 ex.; L₈₀, 28.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 9 ex.; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 33 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Iğdır provinces [30-50].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Transcaucasia, Europa, Afghanistan, Iran, Kazakhstan, Turkmenia and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. TUE [62].

***Laccobius (Microlaccobius) alternus* Motschulsky, 1855**

Material examined. L₈, 21.07.2020, 10 ex.; L₈, 19.07.2021, 21 ex.; L₁₂, 03.09.2021, 1 ex.; L₁₃, 21.08.2020, 29 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 5 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 4 ex.; L₇₁, 15.05.2021, 16 ex.; L₅₀, 18.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₅₁, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₄, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [41].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Transcaucasia, Europa, Iran and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

***Laccobius (Microlaccobius) gracilis gracilis* Motschulsky, 1855**

Material examined. L₂, 31.08.2021, 4 ex.; L₄, 28.08.2020, 7 ex.; L₄, 30.08.2021, 5 ex.; L₆, 27.07.2020, 4 ex.; L₂₄, 20.08.2020, 16 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₇, 20.06.2021 2 ex.; L₃₁, 19.09.2020, 2 ex.; L₄₁, 23.07.2020, 11 ex.; L₄₄, 25.06.2021, 10 ex.; L₄₈,

26.06.2020, 7 ex.; L₆₈, 18.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₉, 14.05.2021, 7 ex.; L₇₄, 15.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₇₇, 16.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 5 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Iğdır provinces [31, 34, 41, 50].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Transcaucasia, Europa, Algeria, Canary Islands, Morocco, Tunisia, Iran, Israel and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

***Laccobius striatulus* (Fabricius, 1801)**

Material examined: L₁, 20.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₃, 20.06.2020, 14 ex.; L₃, 22.07.2021, 2 ex.; L₉, 21.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 8 ex.; L₁₉, 22.06.2021, 8 ex.; L₃₃, 19.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₆₉, 14.05.2021, 2 ex.; L₅₈, 22.07.2020, 7 ex.; L₇, 28.08.2020, 9 ex.; L₂₃, 21.07.2020, 5 ex.; L₂₃, 21.06.2021, 4 ex.; L₂₄, 22.07.2021, 4 ex.; L₆₃, 18.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₆₃, 26.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 13 ex.; L₃₄, 18.09.2020, 4 ex.; L₃₄, 14.08.2021, 6 ex.; L₅₆, 18.08.2020, 5 ex.; L₅₇, 15.09.2020, 7 ex.; L₇₃, 14.05.2021, 6 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [41, 42, 48, 50].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Transcaucasia, Europa, Tunisia, Iran, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, China and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

***Enochrus (Lumetus) quadripunctatus* (Herbst, 1797)**

Material examined. L₁₁, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₃, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₄, 22.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 8 ex.; L₄₇, 22.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₁, 19.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₅₄, 26.06.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₆₃, 18.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₈, 15.05.2021, 4 ex.; L₇₀, 15.05.2021, 6 ex.; L₇₁, 15.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 7 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Iğdır provinces [30-50].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Europa, East and West Siberia, Far East, China, Iran, Israel, Kirgystan, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Tajikistan and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. ASF [62].

***Enochrus segmentinotatus* (Kuwert, 1888)**

Material examined: L₇, 18.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₃₁, 19.09.2020, 13 ex.; L₅₇, 15.09.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [41].

Distribution in the world. Albania, Bulgaria, Algeria, Croatia, Cyprus, Egypt, France, Gambia, Greece, Iraq, Iran, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Libya, Mongolia, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovenia, Saudi Arabia, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Jordan and Yugoslavia [15, 18, 20].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

***Enochrus melanocephalus* (Olivier, 1792)**

Material examined. L₂₄, 22.07.2021, 2 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the studying region (Ardahan) [38, 41].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Armenia, Europa, Algeria, Afghanistan, East Siberia, Far East, Israel, Kyrgyzstan, Turkey, Uzbekistan, Inner Mongolia [41, 58].

Zoogeographical component. TEM [62].

***Enochrus bicolor* (Fabricius, 1792)**

Material examined. L₂₃, 21.07.2020, 3 ex.; L₂₃, 21.06.2021, 4 ex.; L₃₆, 23.06.2021, 37 ex.; L₄₂, 22.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₆, 28.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₇₈, 16.09.2020, 4 ex.; L₅₉, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Iğdır provinces [41].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Armenia, Europa, East and West Siberia, Far East, Iran, Japan, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, China, Nepal, South Korea, Tajikistan, Turkey, Uzbekistan, Algeria, Canary Islands, Egypt, Morocco and Tunisia [58].

Zoogeographical component. TEM [62].

Enochrus (Lumetus) halophilus (Bedel, 1878)

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₄, 28.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆, 21.07.2020, 4 ex.; L₁₅, 20.07.2020, 11 ex.; L₂₆, 22.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₅₉, 24.06.2020, 2 ex.; L₇₈, 15.05.2021, 4 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [41].

Distribution in the world. Cyprus, Denmark, France, Germany, Netherlands, United Kingdom, Ireland, Spain, Sweden and Turkey [15, 18, 20].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

Enochrus fuscipennis (Thomson, 1884)

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₂, 20.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₂, 20.07.2021; 1 ex.; L₃, 20.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₇, 28.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₈, 19.07.2021, 8 ex.; L₉, 21.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₁₂, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₄, 22.07.2020, 8 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 11 ex.; L₁₈, 22.06.2021, 3 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 9 ex.; L₂₅, 21.07.2021, 1 ex.; L₂₇, 20.06.2021 3 ex.; L₃₃, 19.09.2020 2 ex.; ; L₃₇, 21.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 15 ex.; L₅₅, 20.08.2020, 6 ex.; L₅₈, 22.07.2020, 4 ex.; L₅₉, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₂, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₂, 23.06.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₃, 18/08/2020, 11 ex.; L₆₃, 26.06.2021, 4 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 3 ex.; L₆₄, 26.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₄, 15.09.2020, 20 ex.; L₄₄, 25.06.2021, 11 ex.; L₇₁, 15.05.2021, 15 ex.; L₇₆, 14.05.2021, 5 ex.; L₇₉, 16.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 3 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Ardahan and Iğdır provinces [30-50].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Armenia, Europa, Tunisia, East and West Siberia, Iran, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, China, Uzbekistan and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

Enochrus testaceus (Fabricius, 1801)

Material examined. L₁₃, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₂, 26.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₇₇, 16.09.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [41].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Armenia, China, Europa, Tunisia, East and West Siberia, Far East, Iran, Japan, Kazakhstan and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

Enochrus nigritus (Sharp, 1872)

Material examined. L₁₅, 20.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 5 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₇₇, 16.09.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [41].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Armenia, Morocco, Tunisia, Europa, Iran, Kazakhstan and Turkey [58].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

***Enochrus politus* (Küster, 1849)**

Material examined. L₆, 27.07.2020, 15 ex.; L₁₃, 21.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₂₂, 21.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₃₀, 18.09.2020, 7 ex.; L₃₇, 21.08.2020, 13 ex.; L₄₇, 22.07.2020, 6 ex.; L₅₆, 18.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₆₇, 27.08.2020, 10 ex.; L₆₈, 15.05.2021, 5 ex.; L₅₈, 22.07.2020, 3 ex.; L₇₄, 15.09.2020, 10 ex.; L₇₅, 14.05.2021, 16 ex.; L₇₇, 15.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₆, 20.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₃₆, 22.06.2021, 2 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [30-49].

Distribution in the world. Afghanistan, Algeria, Morocco, Spain, Israel, Italy, Canary Islands, Cyprus, Lebanon, Madeira Islands, Egypt, Portugal, Syria, Tunisia, Turkey and Oman [15, 18, 20, 34].

Zoogeographical component. CEM [62].

***Enochrus ater* (Kuwert, 1888)**

Material examined. L₂, 20.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₃, 20.06.2020, 2 ex.; L₇, 28.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₈, 19.07.2021, 2 ex.; L₃₆, 22.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₉, 20.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₁, 23.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₄₂, 26.07.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the research area [41].

Distribution in the world. Algeria, Egypt, Azerbaijan, China (Xinjiang), Ukraine, Kyrgyzstan, Turkey and Russia (Crimea) [69].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

***Berosus spinosus* (Steven, 1808)**

Material examined. L₆₈, 18.08.2020, 3 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Iğdır provinces [48].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Europa, Tunisia, Afghanistan, Iran, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Turkey, Uzbekistan, West Siberia and China [58].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

***Hydrobius fuscipes* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: L₃, 20.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₅, 20.07.2020, 27 ex.; L₁₅, 27.07.2021, 19 ex.; L₂₈, 18.09.2020, 5 ex.; L₃₀, 18.09.2020, 3 ex.; L₃₁, 19.09.2020, 2 ex.; L₃₂, 23.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₇, 21.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₃₇, 22.05.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₀, 23.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₆, 23.06.2021, 9 ex.; L₄₇, 22.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₅₅, 20.08.2020, 3 ex.; L₇₈, 16.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₀, 18.08.2020, 2 ex.; L₅₀, 25.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₆₃, 18.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₇, 27.08.2020, 1 ex. L₇₆, 14.05.2021, 2 ex.

Remark. This is the first registration for the provinces of Ardahan and Iğdır [30-47].

Distribution in the world. Azerbaijan, Europa, Algeria, Tunisia, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Far East, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, China, Syria, Turkey and Uzbekistan [58].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

Family Noteridae Thomson, 1860

***Noterus clavicornis* (De Geer, 1774)**

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 7 ex.; L₂, 20.05.2021, 7 ex.; L₂, 20.07.2021, 1 ex.; L₅, 21.08.2020, 4 ex.; L₆, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₆, 23.06.2021, 8 ex.; L₁₃, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₅, 20.07.2020, 35 ex.; L₁₆, 18.09.2020, 16 ex.; L₁₇, 17.07.2021, 3 ex.; L₂₁, 21.07.2020, 7 ex.; L₂₇, 22.06.2021, 2 ex.; L₃₅, 14.08.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₆, 20.08.2020, 5 ex.; L₃₆,

22.06.2021, 11 ex.; L₃₉, 21.08.2020, 10 ex.; L₅₃, 22.07.2020, 10 ex.; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 6 ex.; L₆₈, 27.08.2020, 50 ex.; L₆₈, 15.05.2021, 15 ex.; L₇₄, 15.09.2020, 11 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the studying region [42, 46, 49].

Distribution in the world. Afghanistan, Albania, Algeria, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, China (Xinjiang), Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Egypt, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain (UK), Greece, Hungary, India, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lebanon, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Syria, Turkmenistan, Turkey, and the former Yugoslavia (Serbia, Montenegro) [58].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

Family Dryopidae Billberg, 1820

Dryops rufipes (Krynicky, 1832)

Material examined. L₈, 21.07.2020, 2 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from the studying region [5-6, 44].

Distribution in the world. Afghanistan, Austria, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Egypt, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Israel, Italy, Lebanon, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Syria, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and Uzbekistan [11, 70].

Zoogeographical component. TEM [62].

Family Heteroceridae MacLeay, 1825

Heterocerus fenestratus (Thunberg, 1784)

Material examined. L₉, 21.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₁₀, 20.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₂₂, 21.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₁, 19.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₆, 28.08.2020 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Iğdır province [5,11,59].

Distribution in the world. Afghanistan, Albania, Algeria, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bosnia Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Canada, Chile, China, Taiwan, Xizang, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Egypt, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Iraq, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Laos, Latvia, Lebanon, Lithuania, Malaysia, Moldavia, Mongolia, Montenegro, Morocco, Netherlands, North Korea, Philippines, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Slovakia, Slovenia, South Korea, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Syria, Tajikistan, Thailand, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, United States of Amerika, Uzbekistan, Vietnam, Yemen and the Southern Hemisphere [5, 11, 59].

Zoogeographical component. OLA [62].

Family Elmidae Curtis, 1830

Elmis maugetii maugetii Latreille, 1802

Material examined. L₆₂, 24.06.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₈, 27.08.2020, 1 ex.

Remark. Recorded for the first time from Iğdır province [6, 31, 60].

Distribution in the world. Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey and Ukraine [6, 31, 60, 71].

Zoogeographical component. W-PAL [62].

Family Hydraenidae **Mulsant, 1844**

Hydraena helena **Orchymont, 1929**

Material examined. L₁, 20.07.2020, 2 ex.; L₁₇, 17.07.2021, 1 ex.; L₃₁, 19.09.2020, 1 ex.; L₇₄, 15.09.2020, 10 ex.; L₃₆, 23.06.2021, 1 ex.; L₄₃, 26.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₅₃, 23.07.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₆, 28.08.2020 6 ex., L₈₀, 28.08.2020, 1 ex; L₈₀, 14.05.2021, 8 ex.

Remark. New record for Kars and Iğdır provinces [6, 22, 61].

Distribution in the world. Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia, Turkey and Yugoslavia (Serbia, Montenegro) [22, 61].

Zoogeographical component. EUR [62].

Ochthebius striatus (**Laporte de Castelnau, 1840**)

Material examined. L₅₅, 20.08.2020, 1 ex.; L₆₈, 27.08.2020, 10 ex.; L₆₈, 15.05.2021, 15 ex.; L₇₀, 15.05.2021, 33 ex.

Remark. New record for Iğdır province [6,22,40,61].

Distribution in the world. Albania, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Lebanon, Russia, South European Territory, Turkey and Yugoslavia (Serbia, Montenegro) [22,61].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].

Limnebius rubropiceus **Kuwert, 1890**

Material examined. L₁₇, 17.07.2021, 1 ex.; L₇₁, 15.05.2021, 1 ex.

Remark. New record for Iğdır province [6, 22, 61].

Distribution in the world. Armenia, Greece, Macedonia and Turkey [6, 22, 61].

Zoogeographical component. SIE [62].